

Information Extraction from German Medieval Charters Abstracts

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Diplomatics Research of Late Medieval Charters

Historical Charters:

- Documents that record and formally express a legally enforceable act
- Reflect the evolving relationships between rulers and subjects, as well as between different social and economic groups
- Crucial to understanding the development of legal and political systems throughout history

Diplomatics Research of Late Medieval Charters

Diplomatics:

- Auxiliary sciences of history scholarly field
- Concerned with carrying in-depth critical analysis of historical documents
 - Understanding documentary practices:
 - Conventional visual features
 - Writing protocols and used textual patterns/formulae
- Applications:
 - Determining the authenticity of charters
 - Relating the information which the charters present to previously known facts

Diplomatics Research of Late Medieval Charters

Traditional Diplomatics focuses on a limited number of charters at a time:

- Individual chanceries
- Collections of single institutions
- Practices of one country or region

**Surge in documentation of legal activity
during the late medieval period**

Monasterium.net Platform [1]

Period	Nbr of charters
Before 1300	66,156
14th century	156,098
15th century	164,376
16th century	81,751
17th century	56,271
Not Dated	132,898

Diplomatics Research of Late Medieval Charters

Need for '**Digital Diplomatics**':

- Making use of the large amount of digitized historical records
- Incorporating digital methods into traditional diplomatics methodologies

Harnessing **digital technologies** to:

- Enable the study of large amounts of charters produced in different regions and/or institutions
- Open up the possibility of capturing a larger perspective on documentary practices

Information Extraction from Late Medieval Charters

Information Extraction:

- Facilitates the semantic analysis of text
- Allows for automatic exploration and querying of massive datasets in a short period
- First relevant step: **Named Entity Recognition (NER)**

NER of Medieval Charters

- Several studies: [Aguilar et al., 2016](#); [Chastang et al., 2021](#); [Aguilar et al., 2021](#); [Aguilar 2022](#); [Monroc et al., 2022](#)
- Testing the applicability of contemporary NER techniques to few medieval languages:
 - Feature-based Machine Learning methods vs. Deep Learning-based methods
- Restrictive set of annotated corpora to train and evaluate models (shared among multiple studies):
 - High-quality manually compiled datasets
 - Doesn't account for the realistic case of noisy data due to HTR errors ([Boroş et al., 2020](#))

Proposal: Investigate NER of Charters Abstracts

Charter Abstract:

- Brief summary of a charter legal content
- Written by expert historian in more modern language

Advantages:

- More accessible in digital archives than charters images
- Contain important 'diplomats search relevant' entities

Charter: Salzburg, Erzstift (798-1806) AUR 1431 - 1434

[Fonds](#) > [AT-HHStA](#) > [SbgE](#) > [AUR_1431-1434.1](#)

Signature: AUR 1431 - 1434

[Download XML](#) [PDF- Export](#)

[< Previous Charter](#) 5272 of 12042 [next charter >](#)

Add bookmark
Edit charter (old editor)

▼ Graphics

1 2

▲ Abstract

30. Juni 1431, [Salzburg](#)

Quittung des **Oswald Törringer**, Hauptmann und Pfleger zu Mühldorf, für sich und andere, dass sie wegen ihres Soldes am Zug gegen Böhmen vom Erzstift ausgerichtet seien.

“Receipt from **Oswald Törringer**, captain and steward of Mühldorf, for himself and others, that they received their pay for the campaign against Bohemia from the **archbishopric**.”

NER of Charters Abstracts

Original Abstract:

“Christian Lanthaler (Länthaler), Bürger zu St. Veit im Pongau, verkauft seine Behausung und Hofstatt zu St. Veit dem Leonhard Ratzenberger.”

EN Translation:

“**Christian Lanthaler** (Länthaler), citizen of **St. Veit im Pongau**, sells his house and farmstead in **St. Veit** to **Leonhard Ratzenberger**.”

Abstract could:

- Include quote from text of original charter
- Be written in slightly outdated language form

Experiment

Starting Point:

- **How well could an open-source Standard German NER system function in this setting?**

Experiment:

- Evaluate the performance of a **pre-trained Standard German model** against that of a **custom-made NER model**

Building Ground-Truth Dataset

Ground-Truth Dataset:

- 2394 German abstracts of **138675 tokens** (randomly selected)
- From archive of the Archbishopric of Salzburg [2] and Melk Abbey records [3]
- Tagged NE types: **person, place, and organization** names
- Tagging scheme: **BIO format**
- Partitions: **70% training** set, **15% validation** set, **15% testing** set

Custom and Pre-trained NER Model

Trained NER Model:

- Using training and validation sets
- Taking advantage of the spaCy training functionality to train model

Pre-trained Standard German Model:

- spaCy large German pre-trained model [4]
- Architecture: CNN

Evaluation Results

Model /	Standard German Model			Trained NER Model		
Category	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
B-PERS	0.62	0.56	0.59	0.89	0.85	0.87
I-PERS	0.89	0.48	0.62	0.92	0.82	0.87
B-LOC	0.34	0.69	0.46	0.73	0.53	0.61
I-LOC	0.14	0.20	0.17	0.37	0.11	0.17
B-ORG	0.11	0.05	0.07	0.81	0.65	0.72
I-ORG	0.21	0.05	0.07	0.83	0.67	0.74

Perspectives

Since our training data is relatively small:

- Results imply that charters abstracts are too domain-specific to be handled easily by regular NER systems

Future Research:

- Creating bigger charters abstracts dataset
- Testing more cutting-edge models (BiLSTM-CRF, Embeddings)
- Exploring fine-grained NER

References

[1] <https://www.monasterium.net/mom/home>

[2] <https://www.monasterium.net/mom/AT-HHStA/SbgE/fond>

[3] <https://www.monasterium.net/mom/AT-StiAM/MelkOSB/fond>

[4] https://spacy.io/models/de#de_core_news_lg

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Thank You for
Listening!!